

1 THEORY AND METHODOLOGY FOR ORGANIZING DRAWING LESSONS THROUGH A PEN FOR STUDENTS OF THE COURSE

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Annotation. In the areas of Fine Arts of higher educational institutions, such a framework as the formation of professional skills and literacy in painting, a worldview. In fulfilling this responsibility, the Fine Arts touring drawing through a pencil in all plays the main role. Drawing through a pencil is used not only in the representation of the plastic structure of forms on the surface of the plane in all types of Fine Arts, applied art, design, graphics and the like, but also as a science that teaches us to understand and think about its constructive basis.

Keywords: drawing through a pencil, image, imagination, composition, fine art, applied art, design, graphics.

"Drawing through a pencil" was originally considered an image-defining term when creating an image using lines at the beginning of the XVIII century, entering as an area that introduces the important features of an item of all art types, defining its shape, size, structure and character. Drawing through a pencil is also a means of reflecting thought, emotion and imagination in any composition and design. The great painter and sculptor of the Renaissance, Michelangelo Buonarroti, did not in vain say that "drawing through a pencil is the color-image, sculpture, the highest point of architecture, the root and source of all sciences."

Drawing through a pencil is the basis of all types of Fine Arts. As an artist or designer plans a sketch, a project, and the like, he turns to drawing through a pencil in the process of his creation and is based. He describes and expresses his observations, his research on the compositions of a large work, first with his initial drawings in pencil. When creating works of art, these executed drawings serve as an auxiliary resource to the artist. In order to correctly depict the original shape of objects on the surface of paper or fabric with high skill, it is necessary to perfectly master the pictorial qualification and apply it in practice - to learn to draw, based on nature, as well as memory and imagination. Of course, to complete such creative tasks, a person is required to have the ability to paint and work on himself continuously, tirelessly, as well as to develop this talent.

One of the main tasks of drawing through a pencil involves the formation in young people of imaging skills, knowledge, skills and competencies resulting from the development of one's own talents and abilities. It provides for the student to know the laws of representation and be able to use them correctly.

Drawing through a pencil can also be an independently completed work of art, among other types of art. Many of the cartoons executed in Tush, sanguina, pastel, sauce, pencil have been featured in various world art museums and exhibitions. Seeing and observing the training of drawing through a pencil, it is necessary to correctly describe, to perceive being, to

form the organs of hand, mind and intuition, and not only to the future artist, but also to people in various fields of profession

Pencil drawing training is the main subject in the training of future teacher-artists, among other specialist disciplines. Drawing classes by Pencil are taught to students through theoretical and practical training in stages. It should be noted that among the practical classes, theoretical knowledge becomes important to future educators in their scientific and creative activities after completing their acquisition of knowledge.

The realistic depiction of things and forms in existence is of great importance not only to give students, not only practical knowledge and skills, but also to cultivate their common worldviews. The art of realistic representation is incomparable in the development of skills for future educators to express young artists in truthful images. It should be noted separately that the study of painting is of great importance for students to cultivate their aesthetic tastes, as well as realistic depictions of surrounding bodies. The study of the basics of drawing is based on the principle of describing in methodological consistency, depending on the thing itself. The mature competence of the future teacher of Fine Arts and design depends not only on the deep mastery of practical knowledge, but also on the thoroughness of his theoretical training in the field of imaging art.

Figure 1.

When drawing through a training Pencil, it is necessary to give a complete picture of the shape, plastic, proportion and construction of the Natura. Studying forms using Natura is a great opportunity in the artist's work. In addition, we need to be able to perceive nature. The surrounding being is not as much as it seems to us in reality, for example, as parallel lines meet each other, sharp corners are sometimes sharp, sometimes impenetrable, and the circle appears in the form of an ellipse, the pencil height appears equal to the building height as in Figure 1, and it is difficult to understand others without pencil drawing, perspective exercises. In addition to explaining optical phenomena, perspective also Armes the artist with ways to depict shapes in different states of their turns in an environment (space). It also makes it possible to understand ways to describe the location at different levels of distance.

Figure 2.

Realistic painting teaches you to master the basics, styles and skills, to know the sequence in the depiction, and to be able to use different materials. In theoretical and practical training, it is important that the future educator receives knowledge and improves his qualifications, learns to work with various pencils and forms his abilities, is able to effectively use it in practice.

All shapes in nature, and even the human body, are complex plastic shapes composed of compounds that resemble various geometric shapes in itself (for example: sphere, cube, cone, cylinder, pyramid, prism, etc.) (Figure 2).

Therefore, the initial training in drawing through a pencil will focus on mastering the basic laws and regulations of Fine Art and drawing simple geometric shapes in different positions and angles based on these laws.

With a special emphasis on improving the skills of students in the field of Fine Arts, it is advisable for every young specialist to keep in mind the thoughts expressed by famous figures in this field and make them a motto in the process of work. The main task of visual art is to develop the ability to feel the presence in the future educator and be able to describe it live in the process of his work, and to fully convey information about Uzbek and world art to the younger generation.

In the field of Fine Arts, the process of forming skills in practical terms is carried out through the exercises of life-image of nature. Many scientific articles, educational literature and brochures were written about this, and as early as the ancient Renaissance, artist-creators expressed their opinions through their world-famous works of art and methodological research.

To correctly describe the form, the student must first learn to clearly imagine and see its specific aspects. For a young and beginning artist, this is not an easy task and requires constant theoretical and practical training.

People by nature imagine all things, objects and their shape in different ways. This, in turn, is another example of the fact that each person depends on his imagination, character and vision.

To do this, teachers of Fine Arts and design must have sufficient knowledge, skills and level of creativity in graphics. It is known that drawing through a pencil is characterized as a separate type of art, as well as being the main criterion and basis in mastering the Fine Arts.

Art creators and educators who are well versed in the secrets of drawing through a pencil will be able to realize their feedback, emotions faster, as well as more accurately. One of our scientists did not say for nothing that "imaging means observation, creation, invention." In the process of working drawing through a pencil, students are required to know the following:

Figure 3.

- theoretical information about the art of graphics;
- Materials used in drawing through a pencil, rules and instructions for their preparation;
- the basics of painting work when drawing from Natura through a pencil;
- Knowledge and theoretical concepts of the laws of perspective contraction in the process of image construction when drawing through a pencil;
- composition solution of the image being executed in pencil;
- To have experience and competence in completing work in drawing through a pencil;
- When drawing through a pencil, it is necessary that they carry out a number of goals and tasks, such as ways and methods of shaping the work performed with a pencil.

In addition, when perfectly mastering the basics of the above mentioned requirement and law, small specialists in the fine arts should be able to perform the processes from simple geometric shapes (Figure 3), fruit and polish products, household items, fabric planks and dresses, musical instruments, sports equipment, man in motion, animals and poultry and various manifestations of nature in drawing through a pencil.

It is of great importance to introduce the future pedagogical artists to the lives and creative activities of the great artist and individuals who have inherited a lot of theoretical, practical knowledge in the field of Fine Arts, to deeply teach their works and to attract copies from them.

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